

AiRT

Flight plan

Flight session

FLIGHT SETTINGS

Max vertical speed

A vertical slider control with a dark blue handle at the bottom. To its right is a light gray rounded rectangle containing the text "9.9m/s".

9.9m/s

Max rotation speed

A horizontal slider control with a dark blue handle on the left. To its left is a light gray rounded rectangle containing the text "40°/s".

40°/s

PILOT SETTINGS

Max altitude

999m

Max tilt angle

365°

CREDITS

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Fixed heights

4.25m

3.12m

1.25m

Min safety distance

2.45

ACCEPT

- 4.25m
- 3.12m
- 1.25m

SCAN

Planning >

WARNING

**Maintain a safe distance from the drone.
You will need to hold the take off button for 3 seconds.
Your current position will be set as the home point.**

< Change mode

CONTINUE

- 4.25m
- 3.12m
- 1.25m

TAKE OFF

< Change mode

WARNING

**You are about to control the drone manually.
Afterwards, you will need to reset the
system to begin a new flight session.**

CANCEL

ACCEPT

CALIBRATION

MANUAL

AUTO

CALIBRATION

MANUAL

AUTO

CALIBRATION

MANUAL

AUTO

CALIBRATION

MANUAL

AUTO

